

Three-tone excitation of the human cochlea

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Abstract. Typical sounds we hear, including speech and music, are a complex combination of tones. Yet, owing to the challenges involved in understanding the processing of sounds in the cochlea, complex sound inputs are seldom explored. Among a few exceptions, three tones are used in acquiring the Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emissions (DPOAE) suppression tuning curves (STCs) for indirect assessment of the cochlear tuning. As the first step, DPOAE is measured in healthy human subjects and compared with predictions made using the non-linear human mechanical-electrical-acoustic model. The next step will be to measure DPOAE STC and compare it with the observations reported by other researchers similar to Abdala et al. (1996) and also to derive insights into the mechanisms involved in suppression.

INTRODUCTION

Otoacoustic Emissions (OAEs) are sounds that are produced by a healthy inner ear. OAEs originate inside the cochlea due to the active electromotility of the outer hair cells. Study on the OAEs helps in the analysis of the cochlea health of the human subject [1,2]. Distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs) offer a frequency-specific non-invasive study for hearing testing. The DPOAEs are produced when two pure tones (f_1, f_2) are presented simultaneously to the healthy ear. Owing to cochlear nonlinearities, many combination tones are produced inside the cochlea and are emitted out of the ear, the prominent one being the cubic distortion product (CDP) at the frequency $2f_1 - f_2$. DPOAE testing is especially valuable in detecting early signs of hearing loss and assessing cochlear function in various clinical populations, such as infants, children, and individuals with noise-induced hearing loss.

It has been shown that the CDP is suppressed by adding a third tone, and this suppression is stronger as the third tone gets closer to f_2 [3,1,2]. A suppression tuning curve can be obtained by varying the level of external tone (suppressor) required to suppress the CDP by a determined amount, such as by 6 dB, and is plotted as a function of the suppressor frequency [4].

Abdala et. al. [5,6] investigated STC with two objectives: to examine the characteristics of DPOAE iso-STCs from adult humans with normal hearing and contrast the adult DPOAE STCs to the same subjects' forward-masked psychoacoustic tuning curves (PTCs) and to record DPOAE STCs in newborns and assess the cochlear tuning maturation. The results implied that (a) suppression of the CDP may offer an indirect indicator of human cochlear frequency resolution and (b) cochlear tuning and related active mechanisms in the cochlea are developed for at least mid- and high-frequency ranges at term of birth. These experiments have shown the study of DPOAE suppression as a means of evaluating cochlear frequency resolution in humans since they are non-invasive and require no active participation of the subject.

The objective of the current study involves measuring DPOAE in human participants as a function of primary levels and frequencies to facilitate comparison with both the nonlinear human Mechano-Electro-Acoustic (MEA) model [7][8] developed in our prior study and with data previously reported by Gaskill and Brown [3]. Further, to record DPOAE STC in the same human subject and compare with Abdala et al. [5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Nonlinear Human MEA model

The nonlinear (MEA) model of the human cochlea, utilized in this study for comparison purposes, has been discussed earlier in Agarwal and Ramamoorthy [8]. The physiologically inspired finite element model of the human cochlea comprises three physical domains: mechanical, electrical, and acoustical, along with the respective coupling. The model incorporates three structural degrees of freedom at each cross-section: BM, HB, and OHC. Nonlinearities are embedded into the model through the HB mechano-electrical transduction current (MET current), which is represented by a first-order Boltzmann nonlinear function. The nonlinear MEA model of the human cochlea, as described by Agarwal and Ramamoorthy (2024), is integrated with the transmission line middle ear model. Integration of the middle ear model is essential for providing direct pressure input at the ear canal and estimating DPOAEs as the pressure at the ear canal.

DPOAE and STC measurements

Human subjects with normal hearing as assessed from their audiometry (performed using MAICO[®] MA 41 audiometer) and tympanometry (Inventis[®] Flute Tympanometer) were selected for this study. The study is approved by the Institute Ethics Committee, IIT Bombay.

The stimulus delivery system presents the two primary continuous tones (f_1 and f_2) to the ear simultaneously using NI-based PXIe chassis 1071. The NI PXI 4463[®], which has two 24-bit analog outputs, is used to generate the two tones. The data collection is done using custom LABVIEW codes. Primary tone frequency ratios of 1.05, 1.1, 1.15, 1.2, 1.25, and 1.30 are utilized. To measure the DPOAE response at various intensity levels, the stimulus levels are set to certain sound pressure levels (SPL), which are adjusted over a range from 55 dB SPL to 85 dB SPL, and the scissor paradigm is adapted to choose the levels of the primaries (L_1 and L_2 at f_1 , f_2 respectively).

$$L_1 = 0.4 * L_2 + 39 \text{ dB} \quad (1)$$

The Etymotic-based ER-10 C[®] low-noise DPOAE probe system is employed.

For STC measurements, a third continuous tone will be included with a frequency about an octave below f_2 to half an octave above f_2 , and levels varying from 30 dB SPL to about 70 dB SPL. This tone will be sent via the same speaker as used to send the f_2 tone as the distortion in the ER 10C probe is expected to be low [14] for levels below about 70 dB SPL.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DPOAE recorded on a normal-hearing human subject is shown in **Figure 1**. The ratio of secondary to primary frequency is selected at 1.22, $f_1 = 5$ kHz, $f_2 = 6.1$ kHz, $L_1 = L_2 = 85$ dB SPL for this data. CDP is at $2 f_1 - f_2 = 3.9$ kHz and $2 f_2 - f_1 = 7.2$ kHz.

Figure 1: The DPOAE recording from a human subject at $f_1 = 5$ kHz and $f_2 = 6.1$ kHz at an input stimulus of 85 dB SPL.

DPOAE measured on the same subject by varying the ratio of f_1/f_2 from 1.0 to 1.45 in the steps of 0.05 is shown in **Figure 2**. Here, the primary frequency f_1 (5 kHz) and stimulus levels L_1 and L_2 are kept constant (85 dB SPL), and only f_2 is varied. The maximum DPOAE is obtained at a ratio of 1.2-1.25, as observed by other researchers [3][12][13]. The predictions from our nonlinear human MEA model reported earlier [8] also show a similar trend.

Figure 2: Variation of DPOAE with frequency-ratio shows the maximum at about 1.2-1.25 (a) Current measured data in a human subject, $f_1 = 5$ kHz, $L_1 = L_2 = 85$ dB SPL, (b) Nonlinear human MEA model predictions at frequencies indicated in the legend, $L_1 = L_2 = 55$ dB SPL (c) Gaskill and Brown 1990 [3], $f_1 = 4$ kHz, at levels as indicated in the legend. The arrows point to the peak DPOAE at about 1.2-1.25 in all the panels.

The CDP can be suppressed by another tone at frequency f_3 . By varying f_3 from about one octave below and 0.5 octave above f_2 , the STC can be obtained. The level of the suppressor, L_3 , can be varied from 5 to 85 dB SPL [9][10]. As observed earlier by other researchers [5], the CDP can be suppressed with the addition of the third tone

As the next step, the DPOAE STC will be measured as well as predicted using the human nonlinear MEA model, and mechanisms of the suppression will be investigated.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

OAEs are frequently used for clinical assessment as a gauge of inner ear health. DPOAE recordings on healthy human subjects are reported in this study and compared with the predictions of the nonlinear human MEA model. As expected, the cubic distortion product or CDP is observed consistently. DPOAE versus the primary frequency ratio (f_2/f_1) is seen to peak between 1.2 to 1.25, as previously observed by others and also predicted by the nonlinear human MEA model. An established method for obtaining STCs using a three-tone experiment has been planned. The future work comprises of recording and comparing the STCs with the Psychophysical Tuning Curves (PTC). The sharpness of frequency tuning in mammals, including humans, can be evaluated by PTCs and STCs. This information could help the assessment of hearing loss. The STC will also be predicted by the model, and the mechanisms of suppression of CDP will be investigated.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by the grant BT/PR40821/MED/32/760/2020 from the Department of Biotechnology (DBT), India.

REFERENCES

1. Kemp, David T. "Stimulated acoustic emissions from within the human auditory system." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 64, no. 5 (1978): 1386-1391.
2. Kemp, D. T. "Otoacoustic emissions, traveling waves and cochlear mechanisms." *Hearing research* 22, no. 1-3 (1986): 95-104.
3. Gaskill, Sally A., and Ann M. Brown. "The behavior of the acoustic distortion product, $2 f_1 - f_2$, from the human ear and its relation to auditory sensitivity." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 88, no. 2 (1990): 821-839.
4. Pienkowski, Martin. "Evidence for a relationship between the suppression of distortion product otoacoustic emissions and hearing threshold." PhD diss., 2000.
5. Abdala, Carolina, Yvonne S. Sininger, Michael Ekelid, and Fan-Gang Zeng. "Distortion product otoacoustic emission suppression tuning curves in human adults and neonates." *Hearing research* 98, no. 1-2 (1996): 38-53.
6. Abdala, Carolina. "A developmental study of distortion product otoacoustic emission ($2f_1-f_2$) suppression in humans." *Hearing Research* 121, no. 1-2 (1998): 125-138.
7. Agarwal, Naman, and Sripriya Ramamoorthy. "Balance in the feedback loop components of the mammalian cochlear amplifier." *Journal of Applied Physics* 128, no. 3 (2020).
8. Agarwal, Naman, and Sripriya Ramamoorthy. "A nonlinear mechano-electro-acoustic model of the human cochlea." In *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 3062, no. 1. AIP Publishing, 2024.
9. Gorga, M. P., Neely, S. T., Dierking, D. M., Dorn, P. A., Hoover, B. M., & Fitzpatrick, D. F. (2003). Distortion product otoacoustic emission suppression tuning curves in normal-hearing and hearing-impaired human ears. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 114(1), 263-278.
10. Gorga, Michael P., Stephen T. Neely, Judy Kopun, and Hongyang Tan. "Distortion-product otoacoustic emission suppression tuning curves in humans." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 129, no. 2 (2011): 817-827.
11. Lasky, Robert E. "Distortion product otoacoustic emissions in human newborns and adults. I. Frequency effects." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 103, no. 2 (1998): 981-991.
12. Abdala, Carolina. "Distortion product otoacoustic emission ($2 f_1 - f_2$) amplitude as a function of f_2/f_1 frequency ratio and primary tone level separation in human adults and neonates." *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 100, no. 6 (1996): 3726-3740.
13. Lonsbury-Martin, Brenda L., Martin L. Whitehead, and Glen K. Martin. "Clinical applications of otoacoustic emissions." *Journal of Speech, language, and Hearing Research* 34, no. 5 (1991): 964-981.

COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Cynthia, King]: I enjoyed reading your paper very much. I look forward to your future work comparing your method of measuring suppression tuning curves with psychophysical tuning curves. Although your MEA model does a good job of predicting the maximum DPOAE levels at higher f_2/f_1 ratios, what might account for poor predictions when f_2/f_1 ratios are closer to 1? It would have been helpful to have information about your MEA model since your reference is not easily accessible.

[Vikas, Lakhmani]: Thank you for your interest in our work. Regarding your point about the MEA model's predictions at f_2/f_1 ratios closer to 1, the unavailability of various parameters of the human cochlea used in the MEA model may be a reason for the low-frequency deviations. The nonlinear MEA model of the human cochlea presented in a conference proceeding (Agarwal and Ramamoorthy (2024)) is being prepared for journal submission. Meanwhile, please refer to the detailed description of the linear MEA model of the guinea pig in Ramamoorthy, Deo and Grosh [*J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 121, 2758–2773 (2007)], and Agarwal and Ramamoorthy [*J. Appl. Phys.* 128, 034701 (2020)].

[Ernst Dallhof]: Time-based waveforms, too, should be part of the study. A study of the DPOAE signal should be pursued with changes in the timing and phase of the input stimuli.

[Dharmesh, Verma]: Thank you for your suggestion. We will do the suggested study in the near future.